
CLR Council on
Library
Resources, Inc.
Twenty-fourth Annual Report 1980

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Council on Library Resources, Inc.
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Acknowledgements

The scholar at his book-wheel is a reproduction of an engraving in Agostino Ramelli's *Le diverse et artificiose machine . . . Paris: 1588*. It first appeared in the Council's third annual report, which explained that "the picture symbolizes the interest of the Council on Library Resources in both the content of books and the mechanics of library service." The engraving has appeared in each annual report since that time.

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1. Mr. Wells was elected to succeed Ms. Ackerman
at the November 1979 annual meeting.
2. As of August 1979.

Academic Libraries: The Coming Transformation

A new decade traditionally stimulates attempts to plot courses of action for the next ten years. This is especially appropriate at the beginning of the 1980s, for it is in mid-decade that George Orwell's apocalyptic vision of society was to come to fruition. While some may be inclined to see manifestations of "Big Brother" in the industrial, corporate, and governmental worlds, the continuing publication and availability of information on many levels assures us that in our country, at least, that kind of authoritarian society is unlikely to emerge. Libraries have an essential role in safeguarding, organizing, and making available the products of historical and contemporary thought. This responsibility is keenly felt by academic and research libraries, whose concerns are the primary focus of Council programs. Thus, in this annual report for the fiscal year 1980, it may be useful to begin by outlining what has happened to these institutions in the last few years and to elaborate on the environment within which they must operate in the new decade. Included in this discussion is a report on the Council's own evolving role in trying to assist academic libraries to meet the future with confidence and vigor. A description of the specific grants, contracts, and programs of the Council that were active in the past year follows the general review.

Pressures for Change

Every healthy organization is continually in a state of transition and change, but at certain times, underlying pressures for change can be particularly disruptive and the resulting problems correspondingly acute and often painful. The 1970s ushered in such a period for higher education. Inflation, energy crises, and economic downturns, combined with declining or stable enrollments, have begun to take their toll, and colleges and universities are faced with reducing spending or finding substantial new sources of revenue. Since the primary source of funding for each academic library is the university or college budget, the library's fortune is inexorably entwined with that of its parent institution.

The major university libraries have become multi-million dollar enterprises, but they are caught in the double dilemma of rising prices and declining purchasing power. Years of prosperity allowed these institutions to acquire new publications at a rapid rate. But the domestic hardcover book that cost \$8.77 in 1969 cost \$22.80 in 1979, the \$3.24 trade paperback \$7.05, and the \$8.66 magazine subscription now costs \$34.54 to continue. The situation with regard to foreign materials is even worse, due to the combination of inflation and the declining value of the dollar abroad.¹ Library budgets have failed to keep pace.

The rising cost of library materials is, of course, only part of the story. Even though many library processes are being automated, libraries are still labor-intensive enterprises; in 1978-79 salaries and wages among the academic library members of the Association of Research Libraries accounted for 56 percent of operating costs, and these expenses also continue to rise. Although libraries are buying fewer books, their collections continue to grow, along with space and maintenance requirements. An academic library cannot reduce its collection or services the way a university might choose to close dormitories and cafeterias in response to decreasing enrollment. A steady-state library might well need a larger share of an institution's budget. In return, academic administrators, painfully aware that library costs are rising more rapidly than those of many other university operations, are demanding of their librarians new levels of performance and increasing accountability.

The economic situation is not alone in forcing a transformation in libraries. Technological advances, particularly computer applications to bibliographic processes, are also prompting change. The addition of computerized bibliographic data bases to library services has invested the library with a new glamour. The promise of "instant retrieval" that the presence of computer terminals lends to reading rooms raises the expectations of library users. Perhaps no other single event has more dramatically changed users' perceptions from the traditional view of libraries as repositories to that of libraries as points of access to information. There is evidence, however, that the new bibliographic apparatus, even though manipulable by machine, may suffer some of the same problems of the old. That is, as Verner Clapp said in 1964, the identification of relevant material not available locally "merely marks the beginning of an all-too-laborious effort to gain access to it by purchase, loan, or photocopy." The new machine-readable data base, like the printed bibliography of Clapp's time, "which in theory serves as the window through which the local library looks out upon that part of the literature which it does not possess," may be, in fact, "a very obscure porthole."²

The last five years have shown, however, that academic and research libraries are not willing to let their windows close, or even cloud over. Increased visibility has brought growing attention to the vital role of the library in the processes of education, of scholarly communication, and in the preservation of the world's intellectual heritage. In addition to their own efforts, activities of federal and state governments, private foundations, university officials, and library associations are assisting academic libraries to develop capacities for constructive change. The 1980s, if not a decade of prosperity, at least hold promise of being one of purposeful transformation.

Two recent publications demonstrate the interest of university officials, scholars, researchers, and others in the future role of academic and research

libraries in society. In 1976, presidents of fifteen major universities explored ways in which the federal government and the university communities could profitably work together. Their findings were published in the 1978 report *Research Universities and the National Interest*. The group considered four major topics: basic scientific research, graduate education, international studies, and research libraries. Their reason for including research libraries was summarized as follows:

*Scholarship in all fields, the scientific and industrial vitality of the country, the national capacity to address public problems at all levels of organization, and, perhaps most important, the ability of individuals to pursue their own intellectual concerns depend to a significant degree on the availability of published information, which is the substance of research libraries. These libraries are indispensable to the preservation and transmission of knowledge and to the creation of new knowledge. Together, they are essential to the advancement of learning, and the quality of each directly affects the excellence of scholarship and research.*³

While recognizing that research libraries bear much of the responsibility for planning their own futures, the report concluded that change on a national scale was needed to help libraries reshape their own internal practices. Federal support was recommended to maintain and improve research collections, to establish a national lending library, to improve bibliographic services and library management, and to establish a national preservation program. Finally, it was recognized that individual libraries, acting alone, would not be able to solve the major problems facing research libraries. Cooperative action would be needed.

More recently, *Scholarly Communication*, the report of the National Enquiry into Scholarly Communication was published. Focused specifically on the humanities, the report attempted to define and assess the roles played by scholarly journals, books, presses, learned societies, research libraries, and the scholars themselves. The 24-member Board of Governors, composed of representatives of these communities, concluded that "new capabilities . . . must be created if the system of scholarly communication is to function effectively in the years ahead."⁴ With reference to research libraries, these new capabilities involved new forms of resource sharing, the development of national collections accessible to all research libraries, the linking of libraries through computerized bibliographic networks into a nationwide system, and preservation.

While these two groups disbanded following publication of their reports, the documents themselves added substance to the work of other scholarly groups interested in research libraries. Both the Association of American Universities and the Association of Graduate Schools established committees on research libraries that have met regularly for the last two years to monitor developments and press for possible solutions.

Technology and Cooperation

The calls to action have not gone unheeded. The reports took cognizance of the recent growth of successful applications of computer technology to library processes. Technology has created the means by which libraries can share bibliographic resources efficiently and has made it easier for them to cooperate. This, coupled with the increasing recognition that their financial state is unlikely to improve, has encouraged academic and research libraries to redefine their traditional goal of self-sufficiency and to begin serious work on developing more effective means of resource-sharing. Increased funding from federal and private agencies is helping to stimulate cooperative efforts and finance programs of national significance. This progression of activity is helping to build the capacity for change.

The relationship of technology to cooperation can be seen in the development of two projects with computers at the core: OCLC and CONSER. In 1968, the Ohio College Library Center, now OCLC, Inc., began to build a bibliographic data base by combining records from MARC tapes produced by the Library of Congress with those introduced locally by member libraries. Now a nationwide enterprise serving over 2,000 libraries of all types, OCLC set the pace for the idea of the cooperative building of data bases and online sharing of bibliographic records. In 1974, under Council management and using the OCLC facility, the same principle was applied to the development of a national machine-readable data base for records of serials, the CONSER (Conversion of Serials) project. In 1978, OCLC assumed management of the CONSER data base, which currently contains over 260,000 records contributed by sixteen participating institutions. In this data base, quality is built in by the use of acceptable national standards, careful control of record input and maintenance, and a process of verification and authentication carried out by the Library of Congress and the National Library of Canada. Thus, technology made it possible for libraries to share bibliographic information more efficiently and paved the way for cooperative ventures. While the Library of Congress has always played a central role in providing the bulk of the cataloging information required by the nation's libraries, it has never been able to shoulder the entire load. Automation and a growing willingness to cooperate allowed other libraries, through OCLC, CONSER, and other projects, to begin to contribute in substantial ways to the nation's bibliographic enterprise.

To serve the needs of scholars and researchers, however, academic and research libraries have stringent requirements for quality control in bibliographic records, for authority control (by which a library maintains consistency in its bibliographic organization), and for cataloging of esoteric materials. In 1974, the libraries of Columbia, Yale, and Harvard and the New York Public Library formed the Research Libraries Group (Harvard later withdrew), dedicated to improving the management of the information resources necessary for the advancement of scholarship. RLG member-

ship has steadily grown and its mission signals how far the traditional attitudes of many academic libraries have shifted. A recent brochure states that RLG exists "to manage the transition from locally self-sufficient and independent comprehensive collections to a nationwide system of interdependencies that will preserve and enhance our national capacity for serious research in all fields of knowledge and improve our ability to locate and retrieve relevant information." Supported by a computerized bibliographic data base (the former BALLOTS system at Stanford University, now the Research Libraries Information Network), RLG members are committed to developing cooperative programs in resource sharing, collection management, and preservation. In addition to the bibliographic services, RLG has established liberal policies governing access by member libraries to each other's collections and methods to avoid extensive duplicative purchasing of particular categories of esoteric or expensive materials. The potential for expansion of these collective beginnings is clearly evident.

Bibliographic Service Development Program

The Council has long promoted the idea of the necessity for cooperative action and has played a role in the development of many of these activities. CLR provided major funding for the developmental stages of OCLC, the BALLOTS system, and other regional networks and consortia, and, as noted earlier, it helped to fund, as well as manage, the early development and growth stages of CONSER. Often it has played a less well-known catalytic role in bringing individuals and organizations together to define problems and determine priorities for action. This work has typified much of the early activity of the Council's Bibliographic Service Development Program, begun in November 1978 with support from seven private foundations and the National Endowment for the Humanities.

Through the Bibliographic Service Development Program (BSDP), the Council is working toward the provision of effective bibliographic services that will meet the existing and future needs of scholarship and research, toward the improvement of bibliographic products, and toward the purposeful control of costs of bibliographic processes in individual libraries. A Program Committee of bibliographic specialists and network principals aids CLR staff in determining courses of action and monitoring projects. Members include Henriette Avram, Library of Congress; Carol Ishimoto, Harvard University; James Govan, University of North Carolina; Frederick Kilgour, OCLC; Edward Shaw, Research Libraries Group; and Roderick Swartz, Washington Library Network. Many working groups, task forces, and committees have been established as necessary to provide guidance for specific projects. A joint effort of the Research Libraries Group, the Washington Library Network, and the Library of Congress to establish the capacity to operate an authority file system is working, for example, with a BSDP Task Force on a Name Authority File Service,

which includes representation from the public library sector. In a similar vein, and in the context of a CLR-funded project undertaken by RLG and OCLC, the Council recently brought together, to assist with planning future work, thirty individuals from institutions that are operating or actively planning online public access catalogs. The payoff for much of this work is long-term, but promoting communication among involved individuals has done much to foster mutual interest in exploring objectives and ways of acting, while reducing destructive competition and distrust.

Collection Management

The most comprehensive data base of citations to publications is of little help if the user who needs it cannot obtain the publication cited. Thus, to cooperative efforts in bibliographic control must be added cooperative building of collections and effective means for sharing resources. Control of collection growth in research libraries in the recent era of prosperity was not an issue; a research library merely bought or acquired as much of everything as it could—and that was a lot. But skyrocketing prices have changed the situation and, as Charles Osburn has pointed out, changes in the way research is performed have also complicated the picture. “Effective collection development in a large academic library is no longer a matter of selecting the important scholarly material from the vast universe of general publications,” Osburn reports. “It has become more narrowly a matter of selecting from among the important scholarly material.”⁵ Osburn concludes with an often-stated thought that is now beginning to gain acceptance: “Resources that are developed, maintained, and preserved primarily for posterity are national resources; therefore, their development, maintenance, and preservation would best be done as part of a national effort.”⁶ Two developments illustrate the growth of this idea: the funding of Title II-C of the Higher Education Act and the planning for a national periodicals center.

The Title II-C Program was enacted through the Education Amendments of 1976 on October 12, 1976, in recognition of the fact that “the major research libraries of the nation represent the bibliographic foundation of our research resources and that financial stringency and increased costs have severely reduced their capabilities for resource sharing.”⁷ In the last three fiscal years, the U.S. Department of Education has granted \$17,000,000 on a competitive basis to both academic and independent research libraries to help them acquire volumes of a specialized nature, create new means of access to their collections, preserve unique and distinctive materials, and make their holdings more available to individual researchers and to other institutions. The federal support extended through this program reflects “a growing and reassuring comprehension that the well-being of research and scholarship is closely linked to the quality of exceptional libraries, and that strengthening the research libraries is in the nation’s interest.”⁸

Complementary to the idea of strengthening existing collections is the concept of establishing new national collections to supplement local resources. An example is embodied in the concept of a national periodicals center, which would house a comprehensive collection of the periodical literature and would be available to all libraries. In 1978, at the request of the Library of Congress, the Council prepared a technical development plan for such a center. Subsequently legislation was introduced into Congress as Title II-D of the extension to the Higher Education Act to continue the planning for the center.

The discussions engendered by various proposals for improving access to periodical literature have made it plain that consideration must be given to the collections of the large academic and research libraries as national resources, as intellectual treasures to be husbanded for the future. It is not simply for the good of these institutions, as Richard DeGennaro pointed out in the 1979 Bowker Memorial Lecture, but because other libraries have been able to depend on the collections of the research libraries to back up their own resources. "The research libraries need to develop their own back-up libraries or central resources pools and other resource sharing mechanisms," said DeGennaro, "not only for their own benefit, but also for the benefit of the thousands of other libraries that depend on them."⁹

Library Management

There is one other area in which a growing capacity for action and change can be detected: library management. Effective management rests on the nature of individuals and on the aims and objectives of specific institutions. Unless these institutions are managed with creativity, imagination, flexibility, and understanding, cooperative undertakings among them are not likely to succeed.

In 1970, the Association of Research Libraries (ARL), with funding from the Council, established an Office of Management Studies. That office has undertaken a variety of activities aimed principally at ARL members, but of use to academic libraries in general. The office gathers information on management practices, analyzes it, and disseminates it through its Systems Procedures and Exchange Center. It provides workshops, institutes, and specialized training in management skills. But its major activity has been the design and operation of a number of procedures for self analysis within individual libraries. Some cover management in its broadest sense, while others concentrate on areas such as collection development or preservation. In addition, the office has embarked on a consultant training program to expand the number of people with skills to assist libraries as they undergo a self-diagnosis and devise means for improvement. Fifteen libraries participated in one or another of these programs in 1979.

The OMS activity concentrates on both institutional and individual growth. In addition, the Council has for several years offered a manage-

ment internship opportunity to midcareer librarians who have the potential to move into senior administrative positions in large academic libraries. Several library schools have also shown concern over the lack of substantial management training within the traditional curricula of professional education for librarianship, and there are indications that new programs in this area may evolve.

Funding Prospects

Although much of the impetus for all of the foregoing developments has come from the libraries themselves, the availability at key points of appropriate funding has been important. There are signs that such funding, especially for cooperative activities, may increase. Federal funding for research libraries through Title II-C of the Higher Education Act has already been mentioned. Since 1975 the National Endowment for the Humanities has devoted substantial sums to the improvement of research collections in the humanities, over \$15 million in outright grants alone, not counting its gifts and matching or its challenge grant programs. The records program of the National Historical Publications and Records Commission, established in 1974, has pumped additional monies into programs for preserving and making accessible valuable archives and collections of records, some of which are housed in libraries.

Increased attention has come from the private sector as well. The Council itself, established by the Ford Foundation in 1956, has since 1977 sought and received funding from other foundations and NEH in support of parts of its program. Since 1977, the Council also has participated regularly in meetings with representatives of a number of foundations to discuss the needs of research libraries and to review pertinent potential and ongoing projects. This foundation library committee does not itself make grants nor does it make decisions concerning funding on behalf of any individual foundation. It exists, rather, as a mechanism to arouse the interest and extend the expertise of the major foundations in matters of importance to academic and research libraries, and, in fact, from this group a considerable amount of money has been provided for a variety of projects. In the words of the secretary of the committee, "it is quite likely that more may be forthcoming; and some major foundations that have not had a tradition of interest in national library matters are now interested."¹⁰

Increased funding will certainly help, but it alone will not do the job. While gains have been made in many areas, the transformation of libraries is only beginning. Those who are responsible for producing, recording, disseminating, or storing information in whatever form must join with users in the restructuring of library goals, the realignment of relationships, and the establishment of new means to meet long-established ends. The 1980s will indeed be a decade of challenge.

1. Sally F. Williams, "Prices of U.S. and Foreign Published Materials." *Bowker Annual of Library and Book Trade Information* (New York: R. R. Bowker, 1980), pp. 454-66.
2. Verner W. Clapp, *The Future of the Research Library* (Urbana, Ill.: University of Illinois Press, 1964), p. 13.
3. *Research Universities and the National Interest: A Report from Fifteen University Presidents* (New York: Ford Foundation, 1978), p. 90.
4. *Scholarly Communication: The Report of the National Enquiry* (Baltimore, Md.: Johns Hopkins University Press, 1979), p. 151.
5. Charles B. Osburn, *Academic Research and Library Resources* (Westport, Conn.: Greenwood Press, 1979), p. 149.
6. *Ibid.*, p. 143.
7. U.S. Department of Health, Education, and Welfare, Office of Education. *FY/78 Abstracts: Higher Education Act, Title II-C* (Washington, D.C., 1978), p. ii.
8. *Research Universities and the National Interest*, p. 97.
9. Richard DeGennaro, "Research Libraries Enter the Information Age." *Library Journal* 104 (November 15, 1979), p. 2407.
10. Richard H. Sullivan, "Foundation Library Committee." *Library Journal* 105 (April 1, 1980), p. 755.

Program Highlights

The fiscal year that concluded on June 30, 1980, was a busy one in terms of grant activity and Council-administered projects. Sixty-nine grants and contracts and fifteen fellowships were active including new awards of \$1,216,000 that covered each area of Council interest: bibliographic services, library operations and services, library resources and their preservation, and professional education and training. While it is useful to categorize grants in this way, it is possible to identify certain threads that wind their way through each.

Research and analysis is necessary to every area of library endeavor, whether it be bibliographic control, collection development, library instruction, or preservation. The Council has always welcomed proposals for research projects that promise to provide needed information in these areas, and it will continue to do so. In the coming year, the Council also hopes to target specific issues worthy of exploration and to involve a broad spectrum of investigators in their analysis.

The need for good library management is another theme that pervades all library activity, for collection development, public services, cataloging, acquisitions, and even facility maintenance are affected by the management practices of the institution. The Council has been concerned with administrative issues for its entire history. Various approaches for improving library management can be seen this year in CLR support for the Office of Management Studies in the Association of Research Libraries and for a project of the Associated Colleges of the Midwest to develop techniques for assessing collection use, as well as in the Council's own management intern programs. Management, operations, services, and collections are so closely interrelated that it is impossible to assist in one area without affecting others. They are parts of a continuum that must be seen as a whole.

Some Council grants support projects that cut across the functional lines that describe the Council's areas of interest. International programs, for example, often touch on multiple issues and are considered here in a separate section. Another category of grants comprises projects of basic interest to the library profession as a whole, such as the continuing publication by the American Library Association of compilations of *American Library Laws*. CLR support made possible the 1,559-page third edition, published in 1964, which led to the establishment of a revolving fund from which further editions and supplements have been supported. The Council recently received the third supplement (1977-78) to the fourth edition. Two full revised editions and seven supplements have now evolved from the initial CLR investment of \$10,500. Also likely to be of wide interest in the profession is a collection of essays to be entitled "Leaders in American Academic Librarianship, 1925-1975" and edited by Wayne A. Wiegand,

assistant professor in the College of Library Science, University of Kentucky. A modest Council grant for this effort was awarded last year.

The following chapters discuss each area of Council interest in turn and outline not only the grants and contracts awarded but some of the CLR project activities as well. In evaluating proposals and defining program priorities, CLR is fortunate to have the assistance of many key persons within the profession who provide confidential advice and counsel, for which CLR is deeply appreciative.

Bibliographic Services

In the Council's *2nd Annual Report*, CLR programs were discussed within the context of certain classes of library problems. One class stemmed from what was seen, in 1958, as "inadequacies of the means of bibliographic access." This involved, said the Council's second annual report, the "devices, procedures and facilities through which a recorded source of information is identified and located. Catalogs, bibliographies, indexes and finding aids of all kinds—including the aids for ascertaining what relevant finding aids exist—are all involved."¹

By 1970, the devices and aids included machine-readable ones, for computer technology had finally been harnessed to work for libraries through such developments as the MEDLARS system at the National Library of Medicine and the MARC (machine-readable cataloging) system at the Library of Congress. But computer applications were themselves expensive, and the problem of helping individual libraries reduce their unit costs remained. After years of careful study, the Council, the National Commission on Libraries and Information Science, and others concluded that the solution lay in the development of a national library and information system that would facilitate the sharing of resources and eliminate wasteful duplication of effort. National bibliographic control was seen as the cornerstone of the system, that is, a comprehensive, economical, cooperative method of preparing acceptable bibliographic records and making them readily available, on a machine-readable or manual basis, to all libraries.

In the decade since, the Council has worked at many levels on pieces of the system. It has provided grants to support developmental work of major bibliographic networks and consortia, it has assisted programs that experimented with the cooperative building of machine-readable data bases, it has provided grants and staff to assist in efforts to promulgate standards that would facilitate the exchange of records, and it has held meetings, established committees, and otherwise drawn concerned parties together to explore mutual problems and possible solutions. By 1978, however, CLR decided that progress in automation, the growth of shared cataloging systems, and the experience of libraries within a machine-readable environment had reached a point where a substantially funded, well-coordinated effort was needed. Such an effort would help to define and solve the political, economic, and technical problems that remained obstacles to the goal of producing bibliographic records for all of the nation's publications and making them available to anyone who needs information. Thus, in November 1978, CLR initiated the Bibliographic Service Development Program.

Bibliographic Service Development Program (BSDP)

The BSDP is working toward three principal goals: the provision of ef-

fective bibliographic services for all who need them, the improvement of bibliographic products, and the stabilization of costs of many bibliographic processes in individual libraries. One of the program specifications is that existing resources will be employed to the extent possible. Thus the program attempts to work with and incorporate the products of the major producers of bibliographic records and encourage those producers to cooperate with each other.

It has been thought for some time that a national bibliographic data base physically located in a single place is unlikely to evolve. A *de facto* substitute seems more likely if the major existing bibliographic data bases, taken in the aggregate, can be considered as the "national" data base. To this end, the BSDP works closely with those organizations involved in major shared cataloging programs: the Library of Congress (LC), OCLC, the Research Libraries Group (RLG), and the Washington Library Network (WLN). Other bibliographic records, such as those produced by university libraries with their own self-contained systems, must also be included in a nationwide bibliographic data base, and ways are being sought to accomplish this.

Through the BSDP, the Council seeks to help others, both individuals and organizations, to accomplish tasks and to undertake activities that are judged to be important for the improvement of the quality and accessibility of bibliographic information and for the operational performance of libraries. BSDP objectives and activities are reviewed and modified periodically to reflect past progress, new opportunities, and, not least important, the programs and work of others who share BSDP goals and objectives. Earlier discussion pointed to the advice and assistance sought by CLR to define problems and establish priorities. In addition, the program seeks the informed guidance of library users in order to respond to their perceived needs and in recognition of the effect on users of changes in the bibliographic structure of the country. The program works to inform the user community of anticipated changes in the bibliographic structure before they occur, so that bibliographic tools can be used to maximum advantage.

Fiscal year 1980 was the second year of BSDP activity and a busy one. Eleven grants and contracts, totalling almost \$850,000, were authorized, including work on standards and guides; access to, linking of, and structure of nationwide bibliographic data bases; and bibliographic products and services.

Standards and Guides. Underpinning any effort to share bibliographic records and products on a national basis is a need for common understanding of the intellectual content of the records and a common agreement on their organization—in short, for acceptable standards. Standards are required both to assure consistency of bibliographic records produced in various systems and to facilitate the communication, reception, and processing of records. A number of BSDP activities support efforts to identify

and formulate standards and guidelines both here and abroad.

In 1979, the BSDP formed a Joint Committee on Bibliographic Standards, composed of technical experts from the major shared cataloging systems, research libraries, the Library of Congress, the National Library of Medicine, and CLR. Its first task was to assist in the selection of options provided under the new second edition of the *Anglo-American Cataloging Rules (AACR-2)* for the machine-based bibliographic services in the U.S. That task completed, the committee continues to assist LC by advising on the interpretation of the new cataloging rules and the impact of these decisions on shared cataloging activities. The group also advises LC on the creation of manuals that will guide the application of the new rules to specialized categories of material, such as newspapers, maps, and rare books. In addition, Sue A. Dodd, data librarian at the Institute for Research in Social Science at the University of North Carolina, received a CLR grant to complete work on a manual for cataloging machine-readable data files, a category of material that was given only superficial treatment in *AACR-2*.

Two specific standards—the Library of Congress' MARC communications format for bibliographic records and an institution identification code—are receiving attention. Recognizing that there were problems with the MARC communications format, a standard that dictates how machine-readable bibliographic records are organized for purposes of exchange, LC employed a consultant to draft a proposal for format revisions, including elimination of record elements that are required only by LC. The BSDP has established a small task force to work with LC's consultant so that this effort might benefit from broad-based review and comment. The BSDP also awarded a contract to Howard and Patricia Harris to review current standards efforts in the area of institution identification codes and to make recommendations designed to produce an acceptable standard. Such a code would identify individual libraries in a uniform and unambiguous manner, which would be particularly useful, for example, in automated procedures involving interlibrary loan.

The requirement for standards extends beyond national borders, for publications of foreign countries and records about them are important to U.S. scholars. Although the principal emphasis of the BSDP is the set of bibliographic problems confronting U.S. libraries and their users, it is clear that in the area of standards, strong international commitments are also required. The BSDP supports efforts to identify and formulate needed standards both here and abroad. To this end, the program supplied a travel grant to Pauline Atherton, professor at Syracuse University, to enable her to attend a March meeting in Rome of an International Standards Organization working group concerned with standard command language protocols. Standard protocols would help users who are faced with an array of different data bases, each with a unique command language. The BSDP

also supports work toward achieving universal bibliographic control, a concept discussed in the chapter on international programs.

Another area of standards activity has been supported from the Council's general funds, but is related to BSDP objectives. Since 1961, the Council has provided partial support for the work of the American National Standards Committee Z39 (ANSC Z39). This committee is part of the American National Standards Institute, a federation of technical, professional, and trade organizations and commercial firms, which acts as the national clearinghouse and coordinating agency for voluntary standards in the United States. Committee Z39 is responsible for standards in the library and information sciences and related publishing practices. The National Commission on Libraries and Information Science, the National Science Foundation, the Council of National Library and Information Associations, the American Library Association, and the National Bureau of Standards have also made contributions to the committee, which is moving toward a program of self-support.

In the past nine months, Committee Z39 published new standards for book spine formats, serial holdings statements at the summary level, and identification codes for the book industry. New subcommittees were established to consider coded character sets for bibliographic information interchange, library item and patron identification codes, guidelines for the format and production of scientific and technical reports, and the format and arrangement of periodicals. The series of general operating support grants supplied to Committee Z39 by the Council now totals over \$216,000.

Bibliographic Data Bases—Linking. There are several large data bases of bibliographic records in the United States. OCLC, the Research Libraries Group, and the Washington Library Network together provide several thousand libraries with online access to millions of bibliographic records. This year the BSDP has been exploring the issues surrounding the possibility of linking these bibliographic data bases with each other and with the Library of Congress. In September, CLR signed a contract with Battelle-Columbus Laboratories to investigate the feasibility and impacts of such linkages. The study will consider the effects on libraries, library users, and the utilities themselves.

Over 250 public and academic libraries were invited to supply data reflecting their experience with the services of one or another of the shared cataloging systems. The initial phase of the study concentrated on a cost/benefit analysis of linking the systems for three major library functions: cooperative cataloging, interlibrary loan, and online reference searching. Battelle also reviewed alternative ways of linking the systems and planned to select three for detailed study. A final product will be an integrated computer model of a nationwide bibliographic network. A group of special consultants was gathered to monitor the study, which was expected to be completed shortly after the fiscal year ended.

Bibliographic Data Bases—Access. An objective of the BSDP is to establish a widely available, comprehensive data base of bibliographic records. This does not mean that these records must be available without cost, since reasonable charges to recover the costs of providing records are to be expected. But unnecessary barriers that prevent access to bibliographic records are counterproductive and not in the best interests of society. The BSDP will seek to reduce constraints of all kinds on access by users to bibliographic information in the belief that the unimpeded flow of information is essential to scholarship and to personal and social well being. To help begin an exploration of the access issue, the BSDP funded partial travel costs of some participants to a March 1980 meeting of the Library of Congress Network Advisory Committee, which focused on that topic. The recommendations of the group are now under consideration.

Bibliographic Data Bases—Structure. In September 1979, CLR called a meeting of the shared cataloging services and the national libraries to discuss the need for a nationwide authority file service. An authority file acts as a dictionary, or thesaurus, for the bibliographic data base it controls. It contains the authorized forms of personal and institutional names and subject terms used to gain access to records in a data base and ensures that all relevant items can be found under accepted terms. The absence of such consistency among currently operating systems is considered a major obstacle to the effective exchange of bibliographic data in machine-readable form. The meeting participants agreed that it was desirable to establish a single, comprehensive authority file beginning with the integration of the files now existing at several institutions (e.g., LC, the New York Public Library, WLN, etc.).

The following April, CLR awarded a grant to RLG and WLN for the first phase of a two-year project that will provide the organizations with the technical capacity to support a nationwide shared authority file system. The grant supports the first phase of an extended development effort by the two networks that will lead to the creation of a telecommunications system to link the files of RLG and WLN and the design of software required to create and maintain online authority files to which both networks can have access. When all phases of the project have been completed, each network will continue to operate its own authority control system, but will be able to share authority records with the other network.

The Library of Congress, while continuing its own large-scale systems design effort, will bring to this project its expertise as the major source of authority data in the U.S. and help to establish the requirements of the telecommunications facility. CLR grants to LC are not only supporting its participation in this work, but are also enabling the library to convert more than 100,000 name authority records from manual to machine-readable form. LC's name authority file is considered the basis for the projected comprehensive authority file.

To ensure that the project is consistent with other activities needed to implement an authority file service for libraries, RLG, WLN, and LC, with others, participate in a Task Force on a Name Authority File Service formed by CLR. The nine-member group will attempt to spell out the guidelines and requirements for a nationwide service in such areas as data collection, file maintenance, online and offline access, standards, financing, and management.

While there is a reasonable chance of achieving a comprehensive name authority file service, there is less chance of establishing such a file for subjects. For subject access, it is more likely that a series of logical subject files will develop, each specialized to meet the unique needs of special user groups. The possibility exists, however, of "mapping" these files, that is, drawing attention to equivalent terms within the data bases. The BSDP plans to explore requirements for subject authorities (by subject field), for thesaurus development, for file organization and search procedures, and for other related matters. As a first step, CLR has provided a small planning grant to the Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute for work on a major thesaurus of art and architecture terms. Another grant to the American Association of Law Libraries will help identify future steps for implementing a national law network (LAWNET).

In January 1980, CLR approved a two-year project that will help the shared cataloging services identify growth trends within the MARC data base. Martha Williams at the University of Illinois Coordinated Science Laboratory will analyze the MARC data base to determine trends and relationships.

In August 1979, the Council received the final report of a related project involving subject control, although it was funded prior to the beginning of the BSDP. In 1977, Iowa State University received a CLR grant for the design and construction of a computer-produced printed index that would provide expanded subject access to the university library's reference collection. The index was produced both in hard copy and in microfiche and totalled more than 1,000 pages and 70,000 entries. Although the index is of primary interest to Iowa State, the mechanized indexing procedures utilized could be successfully applied to any reference collection or other collection component. Iowa State has found that while the index is most heavily used by reference librarians, it is easily used by other staff and patrons and has become a valuable tool for training new reference staff and paraprofessionals. The index provides access points not present in other catalogs, covers bibliographies and series not analyzed in other catalogs, and identifies the abstracting and indexing services that can be searched through an online commercial vendor.

Bibliographic Products and Services. A comprehensive bibliographic data base provides the raw materials for the products and services that are used at regional and local library levels. What sorts of products and services

are needed? Who will use them? The BSDP is attempting to identify issues in this area. Receiving attention in a number of institutions is the idea of allowing the public to have direct access to terminals, now generally housed in cataloging departments, that receive online bibliographic information from a centralized shared cataloging service. OCLC and RLG recently sought and received funds from CLR for a joint study of the approaches, problems, and priorities involved in the issue of online patron access to bibliographic data bases. The project will provide the library community with information of three kinds: 1) current and proposed systems, 2) an inventory of critical issues, and 3) recommendations for research and other work. As the fiscal year drew to a close, CLR was planning a working session of academic and research librarians who already offer or are planning to offer online access to library users to assist in establishing goals and priorities in this critical area. The report itself will be completed by late summer.

CONSER

Reference was made earlier to the CONSER (Conversion of Serials) project, a cooperative file-building effort which has resulted in a national serials data base. The Council funded and managed CONSER in its early stages. Although the project is now managed by OCLC, the Council continues its involvement in several ways.

In 1978, CLR gave a grant to the National Library of Canada (NLC) to allow NLC to publish, in computer output microfiche (COM), authenticated records from the CONSER project. This enables libraries that are not members of OCLC to have access to the records. NLC provides a copy of the microfiche to the Library of Congress for distribution within the U.S., while NLC serves Canada and other countries. A supplement for 1979 was recently issued.

The Library of Congress and the National Library of Canada are the centers of responsibility for the verification of records contributed to the CONSER data base by its sixteen participating institutions. Until early this spring, only the authenticated records were available. Since the process of verification is slow, this represented less than half of the records in the file. During the past year, OCLC produced a "snapshot" of the entire CONSER file as of December 1979 and sent it to LC for distribution. Thus libraries now have available over 259,000 records of serials.

Eight research libraries received funds in fiscal 1979 from the U.S. Office of Education under Title II-C of the Higher Education Act for conversion to machine-readable form of union lists of serials. Concerned that the work performed under the grants might not be compatible with the CONSER effort, in November 1979 CLR and the Office of Education cosponsored a meeting of the grantees and the CONSER participants. General agreement was reached on the need to abide by CONSER standards. An underlying

stimulus for the meeting was the acknowledgement that bibliographic records developed with federal funds should, in the public interest, be freely available.

In an allied project in August, the Council provided partial support for the conversion of the union list of serials of the Boston Theological Institute to machine-readable form through the CONSER project. Completion of the two-year project will add over 6,700 unique theological serials titles to the nationwide data base. The Lilly Endowment and the Arthur Vining Davis Foundation also contributed to the project, which has a total budget of \$66,000.

In addition to the foregoing activities, CLR continues to furnish funds to support telecommunications costs for some of the CONSER participants.

OCLC's Non-Roman Alphabet Capability

In 1978, CLR joined with the National Endowment for the Humanities and the Carnegie Corporation to support developmental work at OCLC, Inc. that would allow OCLC to install a non-Roman alphabet capability on the OCLC online system and to support offline processes in which non-Roman alphabets are used. The first phase of development will focus on the Cyrillic and Greek alphabets with Arabic and Hebrew to be added at a later date. In the past fiscal year, OCLC completed specifications for manufacture of terminals to support the new capability and acquired a printer for processing catalog cards in non-Roman alphabets. Software development has been delayed, however, because of personnel dislocations within OCLC and its projected move to new quarters. The capacity to process materials in non-Roman alphabets by computer is expected to result in substantial savings for those libraries that use OCLC for cataloging new materials and to improve accessibility to these publications for library users.

Library Operations and Services

The first chapter of this report discussed the ways in which libraries are being transformed from self-contained repositories to windows on an increasingly interdependent and complex bibliographic world. The chapter on bibliographic services pointed out some of the specific ways that the use of automation is changing the nature of the environment within which libraries exist. To manage in a constructive manner the necessary changes in library operations and services that must accompany these new developments has become a critical requirement in many libraries. But library staffs are not alone in the need to learn new techniques and adapt to new processes. Library users must also learn to use innovative ways of searching for information and new approaches to the traditional techniques of research.

Recent Council programs have supported work toward helping individual academic libraries to improve management practices and have furthered discussions of the role of the library in the educational process. The past year also brought the publication of two CLR-supported books concerning building planning and furnishing.

Building Planning

In his *Furnishing the Library Interior* (New York: Marcel Dekker, 1980), William S. Pierce, facilities planning officer of the Pennsylvania State University Libraries, discusses the selection, evaluation, and purchase of furniture and equipment for libraries. The author based his work in part on visits since 1960 to over 270 libraries and 20 furniture factories. In *Mason on Library Buildings* (Metuchen, N.J.: Scarecrow Press, 1980), Ellsworth Mason, head of Special Collections, University of Colorado Libraries, provides detailed, analytical reviews of six library buildings and short summary evaluations of 105 others. A recent review said "this volume will soon take a well-deserved place among the top half-dozen eminently useful books on this topic."² CLR grants partially supported travel and other costs of preparing both volumes.

Academic Library Program

From its earliest years, part of the Council's program has emphasized the improvement of administrative practices in libraries. In 1968, the Council decided to formulate a long-range program. Grants were made for a general study of management problems in large university libraries and for a case study of aspects of management in a specific institution, the Columbia University Libraries. In addition, a planning office was established with CLR help at Columbia, and a library research and development unit at the Joint University Libraries (now Vanderbilt University Library) in

Nashville, Tennessee, received support for several years. One of the principal results of the original management study was the establishment in 1970 of the Office of Management Studies within the Association of Research Libraries. In its first energetic decade, OMS has proved to be a key element in the total effort to improve management and fiscal practices in academic and research libraries.

OMS activities can be divided into three basic categories. To develop better information on management operations, problems, and approaches, OMS operates a clearinghouse called the Systems and Procedures Exchange Center. The center periodically surveys member libraries in specific areas such as preservation, costs of library materials, or staff compensation systems and makes available results of these surveys as well as illustrative documents from responding libraries. A second kind of activity relates to the way academic libraries identify, promote, and develop managerial talent within their organizations. The OMS Training Program is committed to helping academic libraries equip staffs with the skills, concepts, and leadership needed to improve performance.

In 1978, the office consolidated efforts centered on its third category of activity—assisted self-studies—in its new Academic Library Program. The Council provided a grant of \$326,500 for this activity from funds received by CLR from the Carnegie Corporation of New York. Parts of the program are also supported by the Lilly Endowment, the Andrew W. Mellon Foundation, the National Endowment for the Humanities, and cost recovery from the participants themselves.

The Academic Library Program assists individual libraries with organizational planning and problem solving and introduces change through a staff-based analytical process developed by OMS. Using specified procedures, participants examine the demands and pressures of their environment, assess operational implications for their library, and then devise improvements in programs and activities. The Management Review and Analysis Program for large academic libraries, the Academic Library Development Program for mid-sized libraries, and the Planning Program for Small Academic Libraries help institutions examine their overall settings and practices. Other programs look at specific matters, such as collection management or, in a program currently under design, preservation. A services development program is also on the drawing board.

The goal of the five-year Academic Library Program will be advanced by the training of up to 100 librarians as consultants to assist libraries in conducting the studies. After a nationwide competition, twenty academic librarians were chosen in September 1979 to receive two weeks of intensive training, which involved individual and group exercises designed to develop skills in identifying, diagnosing, and solving library problems. Following the training period, each candidate is to work closely with an OMS staff member on an academic library self-study project. The second group of trainees will be selected in early 1981 from 153 applicants.

College Library Program

In 1969, the Council on Library Resources and the National Endowment for the Humanities established a joint College Library Program. By 1978, the program had awarded grants to 35 college and university libraries to help them explore innovative ways to enhance the library's participation in undergraduate education. The program was suspended for new applicants in 1978, but because previous grants were for periods of three to five years, the final recipients will not complete the grant period until 1982. Sixteen programs remained active at the end of the fiscal year, with six scheduled for completion in 1980.

Each institution has developed a program to address specific goals and objectives. Success has been mixed, but many substantial changes in attitudes and methods have occurred, as may be demonstrated by the experience of Mills College in Oakland, California, which completed a five-year College Library Program on July 31, 1979.

Mills College sought to bring faculty, students, and library staff together to make better use of the library's general and special humanities collections through exhibits, preparation of bibliographies, class meetings, courses in the history of the book and in research methods, lectures, films, and performances. Great emphasis was given to utilizing the special collections of more than 10,000 fine and rare books and 8,000 manuscripts housed in the library's Albert M. Bender Room.

At the conclusion of the grant period, the library conducted an evaluation of the program, and the final report to the Council included this faculty member's comment describing the revitalization of the library's services:

The difference between the operation of the Bender Room when I arrived at Mills in 1970 and now in 1979 is the difference between night and day. When I came to Mills the room was open only a few hours a week, there was no easy-to-use index of its holdings, and there was no staff encouragement to use the room. Although it was a magnificent room, as well as a rare collection of books, it was usually locked in darkness. One used to show it to visitors by peering through the locked glass doors. Now this beautiful space . . . and the collection of books and manuscripts has become one of the favorite campus spots for both faculty and students. It is an active gallery of changing exhibitions of books, prints, and related objects. It is a meeting room several days a week . . . and most of all is now a place where one can read, touch, and personally handle the rare treasures of the collection. . . . It is my fervent hope that this "new" Bender Room will continue. It befits a college which prides itself on its high quality of education.

The hope expressed above apparently will not go unfulfilled, for Mills received a challenge grant in 1979 from NEH and has designated more than a third of the over \$2 million for library support.

The sixteen institutions whose libraries are still actively working on

CLR-NEH grants are: Pacific University (Oreg.), University of Utah, Clark College (Ga.), Kearney State College (Nebr.), Johnson C. Smith University (N.C.), University of Evansville (Ind.), Northwestern University (Ill.), St. Olaf College (Minn.), Ball State University (Ind.), DePauw University (Ind.), University of Toledo (Ohio), University of Wisconsin-Parkside, Salem College (Mass.), Franklin and Marshall College (Pa.), Lake Forest College (Ill.), and Tusculum College (Tenn.).

Bibliographic Instruction

A basic premise of the College Library Program was that librarians would join with faculty and, possibly, students and administrators to plan ways of integrating the library more closely into the college or university curriculum. Many of the grantees planned programs of bibliographic instruction which utilized a variety of procedures. Some institutions developed separate courses in library resources or research methods, either taught by librarians or team-taught by librarians and faculty. Other institutions preferred course-related instruction. This method enables librarians to enter the classroom and teach library resources especially applicable to the subject matter of a particular course. In some institutions the grants provided the stimulus for the first practical, continuing library-faculty partnerships to develop.

Two grants in the past year specifically supported efforts to facilitate library-faculty communication. In April 1980, Earlham College held its fourth annual workshop on "Librarians, Faculty, and Bibliographic Instruction," and a CLR grant provided travel expenses for twenty faculty members from twelve institutions to attend. Since Earlham's teaching faculty fully participate in the conference, the interaction is particularly successful. One of the participants concluded that "it was excellent for me as a faculty member to meet with a new philosophy of what a library is. The workshop also led me to question what kinds of assignments I am making, and why I am not incorporating more library usage in my classes." A similar conference, which involved academic administrators as well as librarians and faculty members, was held at the University of Wisconsin-Parkside in September 1979. The expenses for the participation of five faculty members were funded by CLR.

Public and State Libraries

While the Council's primary focus is on academic and research libraries, it has occasionally found a proposal from another kind of library to be particularly important to the attainment of broader objectives for the profession. Two grants awarded in fiscal year 1980 can be considered in this category. A grant to the Plainedge Public Library in Massapequa, New York, is supporting a motivational research study to learn more about the factors that might induce non- or infrequent public library users to make

use of public library facilities and services. Dr. Ernest Dichter, a leading exponent and practitioner of motivational research, is conducting the study with the assistance of an advisory committee of librarians from the region.

In mid-April, chief librarians or their assistants from 39 states, the District of Columbia, and the Virgin Islands met at the Library of Congress for the Fifth Assembly of State Librarians. As in past assemblies, held in 1958, 1960, 1963, and 1977, the program stressed the services and functions of the Library of Congress and of state agencies and explored possible areas of cooperation. CLR provided a grant to support this assembly, as it had for the fourth.

Archivists Move to Institutional Evaluation

Just before the fiscal year ended, CLR awarded funds to the Society of American Archivists (SAA) for a pilot program to test procedures for a system of institutional evaluation for archives. The program is based on two years of work by an SAA task force, which was concerned about the recent increase in the number of archival agencies and their relative quality, particularly those institutions that might not realize the commitment necessary for an adequate program.

SAA foresees its program as voluntary and composed of two parts: self-study and peer review. The peer evaluation would be undertaken with the aim of determining how well a repository has directed its resources toward fulfilling the goals and objectives it has set for itself. In the long term, institutions that successfully completed the process would be publicized by inclusion on a list of evaluated and approved repositories. The CLR grant will be used to underwrite the expenses of carrying out evaluations at six test sites, during which the SAA will refine the administrative aspects of the project.

Library Resources and Their Preservation

In his overview of scholarly and research services in the new *ALA World Encyclopedia of Library and Information Services*, David H. Stam, New York Public Library, states that "collecting and preservation should remain the most important function of research libraries."³ Recent years have brought increased attention to the collection development activities of libraries; growing financial constraints no longer allow them to simply sweep up all or even most of the important literature. Stam goes on to explain the collection development function of libraries with regard to scholarship:

*In a general way large research libraries often play an active role in shaping the direction of scholarship itself through their decisions about what is important to preserve for posterity and what is chaff to be discarded. By determining what is retained and made accessible from the human record, research libraries often have the power to determine new directions in scholarship, or at the least to affect the extent of those directions.*⁴

Preservation has always been a critical need, but in years of prosperity the desire to continue building collections outweighed thoughts of preservation. With inflation taking increasingly large bites from acquisitions budgets and with a new emphasis on sharing resources, the need for preservation has moved much higher into the nation's consciousness. An increasing number of articles in the national press are drawing attention to the decay rampant in library stacks. As recently as August 8, 1980, the *Wall Street Journal* carried the headline "'Acid' Paper Threatens Millions of Books" to introduce a story about the 19th century breakthroughs in paper manufacture, which made possible the switch to woodpulp from linen and rag. The new processes produced—and continue to produce—book papers with a high acid content that eventually embrittles the paper and causes it to crumble. It has been estimated that a third of the materials in research library collections have reached a state of deterioration that makes further use almost impossible, and as much as half of the collections may be unusable by the end of this century.

Much of what has been accomplished in the area of preservation in the last twenty-five years has been made possible through an array of grants furnished and programs administered by the Council. The Council has supported a full-time laboratory devoted to chemical research on paper deterioration and the development of techniques to retard it. CLR has sponsored efforts to develop specifications for publishers to follow in selection of paper and bindings. It has sponsored numerous studies, meetings, and

committee efforts attempting to establish a national preservation program, which has yet to become a reality. The needs continue to be great, however, and much more effort is required.

Committee on Production Guidelines for Book Longevity

On May 14, 1979, CLR and the Andrew W. Mellon Foundation invited about twenty individuals with knowledge of paper manufacturing, publishing, and library book preservation programs to contribute to a discussion in New York. The participants sought to gather information about book paper and its use and to identify ways to address the prospective aspects of the preservation problem. Following that meeting, a Committee on Production Guidelines for Book Longevity was formed to carry on the discussion and plan a program of action. The CLR-supported committee, chaired by Herbert Bailey of the Princeton University Press, determined that its aim was to establish a basic set of guidelines to assure reasonable permanence and acceptable durability and to consider the relation of the guidelines to the ways in which books are used. In essence, the committee is seeking to raise awareness of the problem among all those concerned and to develop practical, realistic methods of dealing with it. The report of the committee is expected in late 1980.

Two other modest CLR-supported projects focus on other aspects of the preservation issue. Early in 1980, CLR joined other funding agencies to match an NEH Challenge Grant in support of the Library Affairs Conservation Program at Southern Illinois University at Carbondale. The university library has set up a conservation laboratory, headed by a trained conservator, and is developing training programs, workshops, and other activities to assist libraries and other institutions throughout Illinois and the region. CLR has also awarded a small two-year grant to the University of Wyoming to support direct editorial costs associated with producing the fledgling newsletter *Conservation Administration News*, edited by the university's library director.

Collection Development

Preservation is only one aspect of the management of library collections. Collection management must take into account such aspects as new patterns of academic research, changes in curricula, and the obligations of the institution for sharing its resources on a local, regional, or national basis. While large university and research libraries can afford to assign staff full-time on matters of collection development, smaller academic libraries are less likely to have the resources or expertise at hand.

Last year, CLR awarded funds to support a conference on retrospective collection development designed to advance the knowledge of librarians responsible for selecting U.S. and foreign materials in the humanities and social sciences. The conference was held in July 1979 at the State University of New York at Binghamton and attracted 109 participants. This year,

to assist college librarians, many of whom work in relative isolation, in using their limited resources to full effect, the Council funded a proposal from the Associated Colleges of the Midwest (ACM) to extend the utility of general research on collection use and efficiency of acquisitions policies to the general management of small libraries.

Associated Colleges of the Midwest

The project has two objectives: 1) to provide for these libraries tested, inexpensive, and easily implemented methodologies for gathering data on collection use, and 2) to provide guidelines that will assist librarians in analyzing and using study results. Three ACM college libraries—Lake Forest, Knox, and St. Olaf—are participating in the data-gathering efforts. Project staff will prepare a manual containing a comparison of the methods used in terms of similarity of results, cost, and ease of application. It will also provide step-by-step directions for conducting a study, taking into account the economic and political environment within which it must be conducted and the results implemented. An advisory committee, composed of the directors of the participating libraries, faculty members from each college, and the director of the Atlanta-based Cooperative College Library Center (a cooperative processing unit for a group of historically black institutions) is assisting the project staff.

Resources, Surveys and Guides

From time to time it is important for the profession to stop and look at itself and its resources in order to assess its areas of greatest need. Libraries have traditionally used statistics of growth in material and human resources as a measure of relative success in meeting the needs of parent institutions. Such measures have been especially important in the historically black colleges and universities, which have long been underfinanced and short of resources. Over the past six years, the Office for the Advancement of Public Black Colleges, a cooperative venture of the National Association of State Universities and Land-Grant Colleges and the American Association of State Colleges and Universities, has conducted three surveys of the library resources of these historically black institutions. Funding for these studies has been provided by CLR.

Results of the third survey, conducted during the 1978-79 academic year, were published in September 1979. They showed a similarity with the problems faced by other academic libraries and higher education in general, that is, a slowing of the growth rate of the libraries and a decline in academic enrollment. Twenty-nine institutions participated in the study.

For the last ten years, the American Association of Law Libraries has also used the survey method to derive statistics concerning law school libraries and librarians. CLR has supported this annual endeavor since 1968; the final payment was made in the past fiscal year. The 1978 survey

covered 164 institutions and provided details of compensation rates, operating expenditures, sizes of collections and physical facilities, and numbers of students and faculty.

Occasionally the Council has found it possible to support the preparation of works that help collection development staff select appropriate materials for their own collections or locate required items elsewhere. For example, last year Robert B. Downs, dean of library administration emeritus, University of Illinois, received a grant to prepare a second edition of his *British Library Resources*. Dr. Downs reported in April 1980 that the manuscript had been sent to his publisher, Britain's Mansell, and the published work is expected to appear sometime soon. In late 1979, CLR received a copy of Dr. Downs' *Australian and New Zealand Library Resources* (London: Mansell, and Melbourne: D. W. Thorpe, 1979), which was also prepared with the assistance of a CLR grant. Since 1975 CLR has also been supporting a regular column in *Choice* magazine, a book-selection guide for college and university libraries, that contains evaluations of new magazines and journals. *Choice* is published by the American Library Association and was itself started with seed money from the Council in 1964.

Just as the fiscal year closed, the H. W. Wilson Co. published *A Guide to British Government Publications*, by Frank Rodgers, library director at the University of Miami. In his introduction, the author says that the main purpose of the 750-page work is "to present a broad though necessarily selective view of the publications released by British government departments and related agencies," which include committees, boards, councils and other quasi-official bodies active as publishers. The lengthy annotations accompanying the citations contain much historical and analytical information concerning the British government. Mr. Rodgers carried out a substantial portion of his research during a 1975-76 sabbatical in England, with the assistance of a CLR grant.

Professional Education and Training

The quality and content of some aspects of library professional education, especially as it relates to academic and research libraries, have been persistently questioned by many in the profession, including recent graduates, established professional librarians, library administrators, and faculty members themselves. Concern also exists about the opportunities for post-degree training, especially in management and in certain other areas where extensive specialized skills are required, and about the focus and influence of much library-related research.

These problems stem, in large part, from the fact that academic and research libraries have in recent years been engulfed by a mix of new technological and economic realities and many complicated intellectual and political issues. Taken together, these factors have dramatically changed research library administration and have made it imperative that the operating procedures of research libraries be substantially changed. In addition, their relationships to each other and to other components of the "system" of scholarly communication must be transformed.

While the nature of the times is a valid explanation for present difficulties, it is incomplete. From the viewpoint of research librarianship, the profession itself seems to be ambiguously defined. This fact possibly constrains both educational innovation and effective recruiting and also accounts, at least in part, for traditionally low salary levels—in themselves, a key source of a self-fulfilling prophecy. The starting salary for new library school graduates who entered the academic library field in 1979 was \$13,100, well below that of instructors or assistant professors. Further, the professional school structure is not without problems. It has been greatly expanded in the last twenty-five years and is, primarily for this reason, uneven in quality and presently hard-pressed to maintain high enrollment levels in a time of shrinking demand.

There is no shortage of librarians *per se*. Indeed, there is general acknowledgement that librarianship has the good fortune to count among its members many persons with needed talents and competencies, high levels of intellect and insight, and dedication to service. But the difficulties of search committees in recent years indicate that there is still a severe shortage of first-rate people to assume specialist and leadership positions in the nation's academic and research libraries.

A major portion of the Council's program for the last ten years has focused on issues that affect the nature of the profession and the quality of individuals involved. In an attempt to help librarians gauge their relative economic welfare, for example, the Council sponsored a series of surveys of compensation structures of academic librarians. In 1977, CLR awarded a

grant to the American Library Association for a project to collect data on the ethnic and sexual composition of the library work force and related salary structure. The results are expected in the fall of 1980. The Council has also offered several professional development programs for individual librarians. Past efforts, such as the Fellowship Program and the Advanced Study Program for Librarians, helped individuals enhance their knowledge of specific topics and improve their professional skills.

Just as the fiscal year closed, however, the CLR Board of Directors authorized the staff to expand the Council's program of professional education and training. Subsequently, the Council received a grant of \$650,000 from the Andrew W. Mellon Foundation to meet some of the costs.

Using a variety of methods, the Council will focus attention on recruiting highly qualified individuals into the field of academic librarianship, will encourage development of specialized professional education programs, and will seek to provide additional opportunities for those who show clear promise for leadership to gain pertinent experience. Further, the Council will devote considerable effort to identifying the problems in the field on which research efforts should be focused and to increasing the involvement of librarians and others in the analysis needed to find solutions.

The new program is at an early stage of development, and many of the components were not fully defined at the close of the fiscal year. The intent, however, is to take a broad look at all aspects of professional education and supplementary training that relate to collegiate and research librarianship. An advisory committee will assist in formulating means and reviewing progress. Efforts are under way to secure the balance of the required funds, estimated to total \$1,750,000 for all activities projected for an initial three-year period.

Academic Library Management Intern Program

One of the Council's ongoing professional development programs, the Academic Library Management Intern Program, will continue as part of the new professional education effort. The program is designed to assist in the development of the skills of potential managers for the nation's large research and academic libraries. Applicants must be librarians who are U.S. or Canadian citizens, or who have permanent resident status in either country. Most successful applicants come to the program with approximately five years of professional library experience, usually including some administrative responsibility.

Each intern spends ten months working with the director and senior administrative staff of one of the country's large academic libraries selected for its administrative excellence. The individual programs of the interns vary, but the goal is to expose the intern to the ways a director of a large academic library handles the daily array of long- and short-term operating

problems. Selected from a field of 101 applicants, the 1980-81 class of management interns and their assignments follow.

Beverlee A. French has been assigned to work with John McDonald at the University of Connecticut. A reference librarian at the Biomedical Library, University of California, San Diego, Ms. French also recently completed a six-month, half-time appointment as assistant to the university librarian. She received her M.L.S. from the University of California, Berkeley, in 1973.

Kathleen Gunning will intern with Joseph H. Treyz at the University of Wisconsin-Madison. Ms. Gunning is currently head of reference at Brown University Library, where she has also been assisting the implementation of the library's collection development policy. Ms. Gunning received an M.L.S. in 1974 from Simmons.

Kathleen Moretto will spend her year with James F. Govan at the University of North Carolina. Ms. Moretto is assistant director of the Yale University Music Library, where she is also responsible for coordination of the archival division and the circulation and record library as well as supervision of processing, cataloging, storage, and preservation. Ms. Moretto's M.L.S. is from Drexel University (1967).

Maxine H. Reneker will work with Patricia Battin at Columbia University. Ms. Reneker's present position is personnel/business librarian at the University of Colorado Libraries. As chairperson of the Colorado College and Academic Libraries' Committee on State Classified Library Personnel, Ms. Reneker directed the recommendations for changes in the classification system used by the Colorado Department of Personnel in the twenty-one publicly funded institutions that have libraries. In 1970 she received an M.L.S. from the University of Chicago.

Charlene E. Renner will intern with Joseph Rosenthal at the University of California, Berkeley. As automated records librarian at the University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign, Ms. Renner is responsible for planning and coordinating the activities of three library processing units. She received an M.L.S. from Drexel University in 1964.

Health Sciences Library Management Intern Program

For the last three years, under contract with the National Library of Medicine, the Council has administered a Health Sciences Library Management Intern Program, modelled after its academic library program. This program follows the same pattern, although it lasts for one year instead of ten months. The year includes two weeks of orientation at the National Library of Medicine.

In the spring of 1980, the Council chose three exceptional librarians from a field of 32 applicants for the final round of the program.

Robert J. Sekerak, director, Hospital Library Development Services and reference librarian, Charles A. Dana Medical Library, University of Ver-

mont, will intern with L. Yvonne Wulff at the University of Michigan. Mr. Sekerak received a B.A. from John Carroll University (1963) and an M.S.L.S. from Case Western Reserve University (1972).

Kenneth R. Weeks, assistant to the university librarian, University of California, San Francisco, has been assigned to work with C. Robin LeSueur, director of the Francis A. Countway Library of Medicine at Harvard University. Mr. Weeks received a B.S. in English from the University of San Francisco in 1964, an M.A. in theology from Marquette University, and an M.L.S. from the University of California, Berkeley in 1970.

Joan Zenan, medical librarian, Savitt Medical Library, School of Medicine, University of Nevada, will intern with Rachel Goldstein at the Health Sciences Library at Columbia University. Ms. Zenan received a B.A. in geography and an M.L.S. (1967) from the University of California, Los Angeles.

Support for Students

The management intern programs described above provide substantial opportunities for mid-career professional librarians to improve upon an already well-developed base of knowledge and technical skill. Two other grants made in the past year were directed toward providing enriching experiences for students in the throes of professional education. A small grant to Wright State University is supporting the costs of internships in national agencies or institutions for students enrolled in the Department of History's program in Archival and Historical Administration. Required to give 300 hours of service, the students will probably work in such agencies as the National Archives, the National Trust for Historic Preservation, or the Folger Shakespeare Library.

In the fall of 1979, the Council awarded a grant to the National Commission on Libraries and Information Science to support the on-site expenses of 54 students from accredited library and information science schools who participated in the White House Conference on Library and Information Services. The students assisted conference facilitators and staff in the areas of delegate preparation, resolution preparation, operation of the Conference Information Center and operations of the conference press room and administrative area.

New England Academic Librarians' Writing Seminar

Norman D. Stevens, university librarian at the University of Connecticut and director of the CLR-supported New England Academic Librarians' Writing Seminar, submitted a final report to the Council in August 1979. Recounting his experience with the four-year project, Mr. Stevens said that while he thought it unlikely that most seminar members would continue to write on a regular basis, their writing skills had been strengthened and

confidence in their writing abilities improved. Seminar members published short essays in the *Journal of Academic Librarianship* in 1977 and 1978, and some also published in other library journals. Each participant has submitted an essay for a book to be edited by Mr. Stevens and published by Scarecrow Press.

International Programs

The average American citizen needs to go no further than the local gasoline station to become aware of how events in other parts of the world directly affect his or her well-being. Information produced in every country is vital to decision-making in business and government, to scholarship and intellectual progress, and to the understanding of the forces at play that affect our daily lives. Librarians and information scientists of all nations are the monitors of much of that information. For years they have struggled to produce international agreements on the way information is cataloged and recorded so that regular exchange would not be impeded. Further, an increasingly strong movement among international library-related organizations has sought to improve technical knowledge and understanding of other basic issues, such as copyright, and to establish and maintain basic library and information services in developing countries.

One of the Council's first grants supported the attendance of a U.S. representative at an international cataloging meeting in Lubeck, Germany. CLR has not hesitated since to keep informed about, participate in, and support programs designed to facilitate a global understanding of and agreements on vital issues. In the past 22 years, CLR has made grants of more than \$1.6 million to projects of international scope. In the year just concluded, major new programs have been specifically supported by generous grants to the Council from the Exxon Education Foundation.

Although the principal recipients of grants that foster work on an international level are organizations and institutions, the Council is able occasionally to assist influential foreign librarians in learning of developments within the United States. Small travel grants from the Council's general funds were made in the past year to two such individuals. J. E. Traue, chief librarian of the Alexander Turnbull Library, part of the National Library of New Zealand, arrived in the U.S. in May 1980 to visit a number of American research libraries. In late 1979, Johnston L. Abukutsa, deputy university librarian at the University of Nairobi in Kenya, toured selected U.S. academic libraries with strong user orientation programs.

International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions

In the past decade, the primary channel of Council support for international library cooperation has been the International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions (IFLA). Ongoing Council grants support the work of its secretariat and of its International Office for Universal Bibliographic Control, while a new grant focuses on special projects.

IFLA Secretariat. Since 1971, four sequential Council grants, totalling \$439,000, have supported the work of the IFLA Secretariat as it managed a restructuring and expansion of IFLA's professional program. Revised

statutes approved in 1976 created a professional organization composed of divisions by type of library, by library activity, and by region. As of January 1, 1980, IFLA had 977 members in 110 countries.

The current CLR grant is used primarily to support the work of the coordinator of professional activities, A. L. van Wesemael. The coordinator acts as secretary to the Professional Board and to the new Program Management Committee and coordinates the activities of the 8 divisions and 41 sections and roundtables. He also monitors all IFLA-UNESCO contracts and represents IFLA at important international meetings and conferences.

IFLA has had consultative status in UNESCO (United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization) for many years and has provided an important international forum for the discussion of library problems. In addition to Council funding, IFLA receives income from membership dues, sales of publications, conference proceeds, UNESCO grants and contracts, the Dutch government, and the Canadian International Development Agency.

Special Projects. This past year, from funds provided to the Council by the Exxon Education Foundation, CLR awarded a \$70,000 two-year grant to IFLA for special projects in the areas of 1) copyright of bibliographic records and files; 2) conversion of copyrighted library materials for use by handicapped readers; and 3) conservation of materials, with emphasis on prospective aspects of the problem.

The federation's concern with copyright of bibliographic records and files involves such matters as the conditions of exchange between national bibliographic agencies, the use by commercial networks of bibliographic records provided by a national bibliographic agency, and the legal responsibility of such an agency in distributing records received from other sources for regional or national use by library networks. Findings in this area will be of great use to the individuals involved in the Council's Bibliographic Service Development Program.

IFLA's second area of interest focuses on the need for speedy conversion of copyrighted library materials into formats suitable for use by handicapped readers. IFLA hopes to establish guidelines and to work cooperatively with other international organizations.

In the area of conservation, IFLA will examine the problems associated with prospective prevention, that is, taking steps before publication to ensure that library materials will not deteriorate.

To initiate these projects IFLA will appoint specialists for short periods of time to perform analytical work and to prepare plans of action. While these individuals will add specific expertise to the IFLA staff, over time they will also form a cadre of internationally-minded librarians, who, because of their skills, will likely exercise leadership within their own countries. The central staff will coordinate and monitor the activities of the specialists.

IFLA International Office for Universal Bibliographic Control

IFLA has for many years been one of the most important forces in the promotion of international cataloging agreements. In 1971, CLR awarded funds for the work of its Cataloging Committee Secretariat which, in 1973, presented a long-term program for developing a worldwide system for the exchange of bibliographic information based on the concept of universal bibliographic control (UBC). IFLA made the program a major goal and in 1974 transformed the secretariat into the International Office for UBC. Subsequently, UNESCO also approved the concept as a major policy objective. The Council has supported the work of this office ever since in a series of grants totalling \$364,200. The office also receives support from national libraries and bibliographic organizations, from the sale of its publications, and from contracts and consulting fees. The current grant is scheduled to expire in June 1981.

Much of the UBC office's activities of the past two years stems from agreements on international bibliographic standards and manuals of standard practice reached at an International Congress on National Bibliographies sponsored by UNESCO, organized and planned by the UBC office, and held in Paris in September 1977. The working document for the congress, revised and updated to include the recommendations, was published by the office and titled *Guidelines for the National Bibliographic Agency and the National Bibliography* (Paris: UNESCO, 1979). The guidelines explain UBC as both a concept and a program. As a program, IFLA and UNESCO are working to develop a world-wide system for the control and exchange of bibliographic information, in order to make universally and promptly available, in a form which is internationally acceptable, bibliographic information on publications issued in all countries—in other words, an international bibliographic network. As a concept, UBC rests on two convictions: the recognition that each country is best qualified to identify and record the publications of its national authors, and the acceptance by all countries of international bibliographic standards to control the production and exchange of bibliographic records.

As nations have moved into a machine-readable environment, the problems of compatibility for exchange have become even more acute. A major step toward solving that difficulty occurred with the UBC office's publication in 1980 of *UNIMARC: Universal MARC Format* (2nd. ed. revised), which updates an earlier version and expands it to include consideration of cartographic materials. A number of national libraries, including those of Australia, Canada, Japan, Hungary, South Africa, United Kingdom, and the United States, have already agreed to use UNIMARC as their exchange format, with implementation to take place early in this decade.

The UBC office acts as a secretariat to working groups and individuals engaged in international bibliographic standards work, coordinates meetings of national and international cataloging and bibliographic organiza-

tions, and edits and issues a variety of publications, including the quarterly *International Cataloging*, on standards and other bibliographic matters. A reorganization within IFLA during the past year placed management oversight of the UBC program under a Program Management Committee, which also oversees the IFLA program on Universal Availability of Publications and will be responsible for a proposed International MARC program. The former UBC Steering Committee was disbanded and an advisory group appointed in its place. Foster Mohrhardt, former CLR senior program officer, was appointed in early 1980 to an interim term as chairman of the new Program Management Committee, and CLR provided a small grant to support his expenses in this activity.

International Council on Archives

Another new CLR grant, also made possible by the Exxon Foundation, went to the International Council on Archives for projects related to worldwide preservation and use of archival sources with special attention to third world countries. ICA plans three projects: 1) the preparation of a records management manual designed especially for use in recently independent countries; 2) a symposium to address matters related to the responsibilities, professional environment, and status of archivists in Latin American countries; and 3) the preparation of three separate curricula, to be written in English, French, and Spanish, that will aid in the education and training of subprofessional, archival personnel in third world regions.

The records management manual will contain the standards and guidelines used by professionals working in records management, retirement, and appraisal in the countries most experienced in these areas. Further, it will demonstrate how those practices may be applied to the particular requirements of public administration and record-keeping in the third world regions of English, French, and Spanish heritages.

At the proposed symposium to advance the status and professionalism of Latin American archivists, recommendations will be developed to establish academic requirements for professional archivists and records managers. The proposed curricula can be adapted to suit local in-service training requirements in each of the functional areas of archival operations: storage, arrangement, description, and reference.

UNESCO General Information Program

Although the interests of the U.S. library and information communities are represented through their membership in such bodies as IFLA and ICA, it has often been difficult for the U.S. community to exercise an influential voice within the international information community, particularly within UNESCO. In 1976, UNESCO established a General Information Program to cover all of the organization's activities in the fields of scientific and technological information, and of documentation, libraries, and archives. As an attempt to improve the U.S. position in this international

body, in 1978 a U.S. National Committee for the UNESCO General Information Program (UNESCO/PGI) was formed to serve as the central coordinating body of the U.S. information community, responsible for representing and promoting its needs, interests, and views with respect to the UNESCO program. The American Library Association agreed to act as a temporary sponsor for the new committee, and CLR made a small grant to ALA to cover its expense for the initial organizing year.

In November 1979, ALA Executive Director Robert Wedgeworth reported that the committee had gotten off to a good start and appeared to have been accepted by both the Department of State and the UNESCO Division of the General Information Program as the focal point within the U.S. for matters relating to the program. The committee has not as yet found a permanent sponsor.

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1. Council on Library Resources. *2nd Annual Report* (Washington, D.C.: 1958), p. 7.
 2. Jerrold Orne. "Building Critiques," *Library Journal* 105 (August 1980), p. 1612.
 3. David H. Stam. "Scholarly and Research Services," *ALA World Encyclopedia of Library and Information Services* (Chicago: American Library Association, 1980), p. 497.
 4. *Ibid*, p. 495.

Publications Resulting from CLR-Supported Programs and Fellowships 1979-1980

Part 1: Programs

Bibliographic Service Development Program

Haas, Warren J.; Gwinn, Nancy E.; and Jones, C. Lee. "Managing the Information Revolution: CLR's Bibliographic Service Development Program." *Library Journal* 104 (September 15, 1979):1867-70.

Jones, C. Lee, and Gwinn, Nancy E. "Bibliographic Service Development: A New CLR Program." *Journal of Library Automation* 12(June 1979): 116-24.

College Library Program

Biggs, Mary Mancuso. "Make Your Point: Forward to Basics in Library Instruction." *School Library Journal* 25(May 1979):44.

———. "The Perils of Library Instruction." *Journal of Academic Librarianship* 5(July 1979):159, 162.

———. "A Proposal for Course-Related Library Instruction." *School Library Journal* 26(January 1980):34-37.

———. and Weber, Mark. "Course Related and Personalized Library Instruction." Evansville, Ind.: University of Evansville, 1979. Available from ERIC Document Reproduction Service (ED 172724).

Gwinn, Nancy E. "Academic Libraries and Undergraduate Education: The CLR Experience." *College and Research Libraries* 41(January 1980): 5-16.

Koren, Stefania A. "Student Library Internship Program: Manhattanville's

Approach to Bibliographic Instruction." *Bookmark* 38(Fall 1979):243-48.

Strawn, Richard R. *Topics, Terms and Research Techniques: Self-Instruction in Using Library Catalogs*. Metuchen, N.J.: Scarecrow Press, 1980.

Other

Bruntjen, Scott, and Young, Melissa. *Douglas C. McMurtrie: Bibliographer and Historian of Printing*. Metuchen, N.J.: Scarecrow Press, 1979. Mr. Bruntjen participated in the New England Academic Librarians' Writing Seminar.

Committee for the Coordination of National Bibliographic Control. "The Subject Access Problem—Opportunities for Solution." Typescript. Washington, D.C., 1978. Available from the ERIC Document Reproduction Service (ED 174265).

Downs, Robert B. *Australian and New Zealand Library Resources*. London: Mansell, and Melbourne: D. W. Thorpe, 1979.

Halporn, Barbara. "The Reluctant Publisher." *Scholarly Publishing* 10(January 1979):175-84. Ms. Halporn was a participant in the 1976-77 CLR Advanced Study Program for Librarians.

International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions. *African Legislative and Ministerial Bodies: List of Uniform Headings for Higher Legislative and Ministerial Bodies in African Countries*. London: IFLA International Office for UBC, 1980.

- _____. *Guidelines for the National Bibliographic Agency and the National Bibliography*. Prepared by the IFLA International Office for UBC. Paris: United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization, 1979.
- _____. *List of Uniform Headings for Higher Legislative and Ministerial Bodies in European Countries*. 2nd ed., rev. London: IFLA International Office for UBC, 1979.
- _____. *UNIMARC: Universal MARC Format*. 2nd ed., rev. London: IFLA International Office for UBC, 1980.
- Johnson, Edward R., and Mann, Stuart H. *Organization and Development for Academic Libraries: An Evaluation of the Management Review and Analysis Program*. Westport, Conn.: Greenwood Press, 1980.
- Lagueux, Paul B. "Standards for Networks and the Identification of Some Missing Links." In *Networks for Networkers: Critical Issues in Cooperative Library Development*, edited by Barbara Evans Markuson and Blanche Woolls, pp. 174-84. New York: Neal-Schuman Publishers, 1980.
- Lewis, Alfred J. "1978 Statistical Survey of Law School Libraries and Librarians." *Law Library Journal* 72(Spring 1979):302-39.
- Long, Philip L. *Study of Message Text Formats: Bibliographic Search Queries*. Network Planning Paper No. 5. Commissioned by the Committee for the Coordination of National Bibliographic Control. Washington, D.C.: Network Development Office, Library of Congress, 1979.
- Mason, Ellsworth. *Mason on Library Buildings*. Metuchen, N.J.: Scarecrow Press, 1980.
- Mischo, William H. "Expanded Subject Access to Reference Collection Materials." *Journal of Library Automation* 12(December 1979): 338-54.
- National Citizens Emergency Committee to Save Our Public Libraries. *The Changing Role of Public Libraries*. Background papers for the White House Conference on Library and Information Services.
- Career and Employment Information Services.*
- Continuing Education Services.*
- Neighborhood Information Service Centers.*
- New Technology for Libraries.*
- Serving Citizens with Special Needs.*
- Strengthening the Library Profession.*
- New York: Doubleday, 1979, 1980.
- Pierce, William S. *Furnishing the Library Interior*. New York: Marcel Dekker, 1980.
- Rodgers, Frank. *A Guide to British Government Publications*. New York: H. W. Wilson, 1980.
- Schmierer, Helen F., and Pasternak, Howard. "Study of Current and Potential Uses of International Standard Book Numbers in United States Libraries." Typescript. March 23, 1977. Commissioned by the Committee for the Coordination of National Bibliographic Control. Available from the ERIC Document Reproduction Service (ED 174264).

Part 2: Fellowships

- Benne, Mae. "Information Services in Central Children's Libraries." *School Library Journal* 2(April 1980):25.
- Byrum, John D., Jr. "AACR 1 as Applied by Research Libraries to Determine Entry and Headings." (With Richard J. Ricard, Jr.). *Library Resources and Technical Services* 24 (Winter 1980):25-43.

Council on Library Resources, Inc.

CLR-Supported Projects Active in Fiscal 1980 (unaudited)

GRANTS AND CONTRACTS¹

	Unpaid 6/30/79	FY 1980		Unpaid 6/30/80
		Grants (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	
American Association of Law Libraries, Chicago, Ill.				
Survey of U.S. and Canadian law library resources (\$20,000-1968) ²	\$ 1,000	-0-	\$ 1,000	-0-
American Library Association Chicago, Ill.				
Ethnic and sexual composition/ salary survey for librarians (\$13,856-1977)	6,928	-0-	-0-	\$ 6,928
Secretariat for the U.S. National Committee for the UNESCO General Information Program (USNC/ UNESCO-PGI) (\$2,500-1978)	1,735	-0-	1,735	-0-
Associated Colleges of the Midwest, Chicago, Ill.				
Manual to guide study of collection use in small academic libraries	-0-	\$ 39,830	13,277	26,553
Association of Research Libraries Washington, D.C.				
Academic Library Program (\$326,500-1978)	268,000	-0-	64,500	203,500
Office of Management Studies (\$130,000-1970; \$129,369-1972; \$210,000-1975)	-0-	(273)	(273)	-0-
Boston Theological Institute Cambridge, Mass.				
Two-year serial cataloging project	-0-	8,890	6,308	2,582
Council of National Library and Information Associations, Inc. Haverford, Pa.				
Continued support of the American National Standards Committee Z-39 (\$20,000-1978; \$30,000-1979)	30,000	-0-	15,000	15,000

¹For grants and contracts awarded as part of Council-administered projects, see page 54.

²The figures appearing in parentheses are the total amount of the grant or contract and the calendar year in which it was awarded.

	Unpaid 6/30/79	FY 1980		Unpaid 6/30/80
		Grants (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	
Robert B. Downs, Urbana, Ill. Preparation of second edition of <i>British Library Resources</i> (\$3,000-1979)	\$ 3,000	-0-	\$ 3,000	-0-
Earlham College, Richmond, Ind. Fourth Conference on Bibliographic Instruction	-0-	\$ 4,400	4,400	-0-
Periodical list for <i>Choice</i> (\$7,500-1975)	3,200	-0-	1,000	\$ 2,200
International Council on Archives, Washington, D.C. Special projects	-0-	30,000	15,000	15,000
International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions, The Hague, Netherlands. Professional activities of the secretariat (\$174,000-1975; \$75,000- 1979)	66,000	-0-	36,000	30,000
International Office for Universal Bibliographic Control (\$70,000-1974; \$144,200-1975; \$150,000-1977)	71,756	-0-	40,000	31,756
Special projects	-0-	70,000	6,000	64,000
Iowa State University, Ames, Iowa Mechanized indexing procedures applied to production of subject- enhanced keyword index (\$1,926-1977)	426	(288)	138	-0-
Library of Congress, Washington, D.C. Fifth Assembly of State Librarians	-0-	14,250	14,250	-0-
Meeting on MARC format for <i>AACR 2</i> (\$6,648-1978)	2,016	(2,016)	-0-	-0-
MIDLNET, Green Bay, Wis. Toward salary of a technical advisor (\$22,778-1977)	17,778	-0-	-0-	17,778
Foster Mohrhardt, Arlington, Va. Travel grant to chair IFLA Program Management Committee	-0-	7,000	2,383 (71)	4,688

	Unpaid 6/30/79	FY 1980		Unpaid 6/30/80
		Grants (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	
National Association of State Universities and Land Grant Colleges, Office for Advancement of Public Negro Colleges, Atlanta, Ga.				
Status report on libraries of black public colleges (\$4,000-1978)	\$ 1,000	-0-	-0-	\$ 1,000
National Commission on Libraries and Information Science, Washington, D.C.				
Partial support for library school students to attend White House Conference on Libraries and Information Services	-0-	\$ 10,000 (1,429)	\$ 8,571	-0-
National Endowment for the Hu- manities, Washington, D.C.				
Continuation of College Library Program (matching grant)	-0-	(1,357)	(1,357)	-0-
To support work at LC in developing a national serials data base in the humanities in machine-readable form (\$118,600-1975)	-0-	(6,127)	(6,127)	-0-
The New York Public Library, New York, on behalf of the National Citizens Emergency Committee to Save Our Public Libraries				
Research on future role of public libraries, in preparation for White House Conference on Library and Information Services (\$15,000-1978)	421	(421)	-0-	-0-
Plainedge Public Library Massapequa, N.Y.				
Research to determine reasons for nonuse of public libraries	-0-	29,250	19,500	9,750
Society of American Archivists Chicago, Ill.				
Pilot project for self-study and peer review of archives	-0-	18,670	-0-	18,670
Southern Illinois University Carbondale, Ill.				
Library conservation program	-0-	15,000	15,000	-0-

	Unpaid 6/30/79	FY 1980		Unpaid 6/30/80
		Grants (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	
Carl M. Spaulding, Sunnyvale, Calif. Travel grant to chair meetings of new standards group, the Library Committee of National Micrographics Association (\$2,000-1979)	\$ 1,558	\$ (559)	\$ 999	-0-
State Univ. of N.Y. at Binghamton Meeting on retrospective collection development (\$2,675-1978)	2,675	(793)	1,882	-0-
University of California, Berkeley National shelflist measurement project (\$20,000-1978)	5,000	-0-	(3,293)	\$ 8,293
University of California, Los Angeles Third edition of <i>Handbook of Data Processing for Libraries</i> (\$14,500-1978)	12,000	-0-	2,500	9,500
University of Connecticut, Storrs New England Academic Librarians' Writing Seminar (\$20,610-1976)	2,926	(3,255)	(329)	-0-
University of Kentucky, Lexington Preparation of "Leaders in American Academic Librarianship 1925-75" (\$10,000-1979)	10,000	-0-	4,000	6,000
University of Wisconsin-Parkside Kenosha, Wis. Bibliographic instruction conference	-0-	1,200 (185)	1,015	-0-
University of Wyoming, Laramie Support of <i>Conservation Administration News</i>	-0-	2,000	-0-	2,000
Wright State University Dayton, Ohio Internships for masters degree students in archival and historical administration	-0-	2,500	-0-	2,500
Subtotals	507,419	252,990 (16,703)	277,458 (11,450)	477,698

COUNCIL-ADMINISTERED PROJECTS

	Unpaid 6/30/79	FY 1980		Unpaid 6/30/80
		Grants (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	
Academic Library Development Program				
Seattle University (\$15,510-1978)	\$ 1,260	\$ (3,133)	\$ (1,873)	-0-
Academic Library Management Intern Program (\$100,433-1974; \$92,483-1975; \$95,549-1976; \$98,329-1977)				
1978-79 (\$65,000-1978)	2,651	(1,428)	633	\$ 590
1979-80 (\$58,000-1979)	58,000	-0-	52,190	5,810
1980-81	-0-	111,639	-0-	111,639
Bibliographic Service Development Program				
American Association of Law Libraries, Chicago, Ill.				
LAWNET planning meeting	-0-	2,500	-0-	2,500
Pauline Atherton, Syracuse, N.Y.				
Travel grant to attend ISO TC46/SC4/WG5 meeting in Rome	-0-	1,000	1,000	-0-
Battelle Memorial Institute- Columbus Laboratories Columbus, Ohio				
Study of linking of bibliographic utilities	-0-	233,112	170,904	62,208
Chemical Abstracts Service Columbus, Ohio				
Partial support for U.S. representative at ISBD(AN) meeting in Sweden (\$579-1979)	579	-0-	579	-0-
Howard Harris & Patricia Harris Silver Spring, Md.				
Position paper on an institution identification code standard	-0-	2,700	700	2,000
Institute for Research in Social Science, University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill				
Machine-readable data files cataloging manual	-0-	5,524	3,526	1,998
Library of Congress, Washington, D.C.				
Conversion of retrospective name authority files	-0-	220,000	55,000	165,000
Travel costs re. the nationwide authority file service project	-0-	17,000	-0-	17,000

	Unpaid 6/30/79	FY 1980		Unpaid 6/30/80
		Grants (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	
Travel grant for U.S. representative at Copenhagen meeting on an international authority system (\$1,105-1979)	\$ 1,105	-0-	-0-	\$ 1,105
Davis B. McCarn Rockville, Md. Preparation of request for proposal on analyzing the linking of bibliographic utilities (\$6,434-1979)	6,000	-0-	\$ 6,000	-0-
OCLC, Inc., Columbus, Ohio Online patron access to bibliographic data bases (joint project with RLG)	-0-	\$ 8,150	6,000	2,150
Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute Troy, N.Y. Planning a thesaurus for the fields of art and architecture	-0-	10,000	-0-	10,000
The Research Libraries Group, Inc., Stanford, Calif. Online patron access to bibliographic data bases (joint project with OCLC)	-0-	8,150	6,000	2,150
Toward the formation of a nationwide authority file service (joint project with WLN)	-0-	168,651	42,163	126,488
University of Illinois, Urbana Analysis of MARC data base statistics	-0-	23,463	-0-	23,463
Washington Library Network, Olympia Toward the formation of a nationwide authority file service (joint project with RLG)	-0-	149,666	37,416	112,250
Elaine W. Woods, Arlington, Va. Position paper on standards (\$2,500-1979)	<u>2,500</u>	<u>(2,500)</u>	<u>-0-</u>	<u>-0-</u>
Total Bibliographic Service Development Program	10,184	849,916 (2,500)	329,288	528,312
Fellowship Program	28,263	55 (2,281)	12,327	13,710

	Unpaid 6/30/79	FY 1980		Unpaid 6/30/80
		Grants (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	
Health Sciences Library				
Management Intern Program				
1978-79 (\$83,751-1978)	\$ 21,152	\$ 42 (1,056)	\$ 20,138	-0-
1979-80 (\$86,730-1979)	86,730	246	75,344	\$ 11,632
Library Service Enhancement				
Program (\$220,000-1976; \$194,857-1977)				
Hampton Institute Hampton, Va.	1,742	-0-	-0-	1,742
Travel assistance				
Johnston L. Abukutsa University of Nairobi, Kenya A study of user education programs in the U.S.	-0-	1,500	1,500	-0-
J. E. Traue, Wellington, New Zealand Travel grant to visit U.S. research libraries	-0-	500	500	-0-
Total Council-administered projects	209,982	963,898 (10,398)	491,920 (1,873)	673,435
Subtotals from page 53	507,419	252,990 (16,703)	277,458 (11,450)	477,698
Total CLR-supported projects active in fiscal 1980	\$717,401	\$1,216,888 (27,101)	\$769,378 (13,323)	\$1,151,133

Opinion of Independent Accountant

August 14, 1980

To the Board of Directors of
Council on Library Resources, Inc.

We have examined the balance sheet of the Council on Library Resources, Inc. (Council) as of June 30, 1980, and the related statements of revenues, expenses and changes in fund balance, and of changes in cash and short-term investments for the year then ended. Our examination was made in accordance with generally accepted auditing standards and accordingly included such tests of the accounting records and such other auditing procedures as we considered necessary in the circumstances.

In our opinion, the financial statements examined by us present fairly the financial position of the Council on Library Resources, Inc. at June 30, 1980, and the results of its operations and the changes in its cash and short-term investments for the year then ended, in conformity with generally accepted accounting principles consistently applied.

Our examination was made primarily for the purpose of forming our opinion on the financial statements, taken as a whole. We also examined the Supplementary Statement of Revenues, Expenses and Changes in Fund Balances, by similar procedures. In our opinion, this supplementary information is stated fairly in all material respects in relation to the financial statements, taken as a whole. Although not essential for a fair presentation of financial position, results of operations and changes in cash and short-term investments, this information is submitted as additional data.

Price Waterhouse & Co.
Washington, D.C.

Council on Library Resources, Inc.

Balance Sheet

June 30, 1980

ASSETS

Cash and short-term investments	\$1,981,421
Grants receivable (Note 2)	5,999,258
Prepaid expenses and deposits	7,860
Accrued royalties	902
Total assets	<u>\$7,989,441</u>

LIABILITIES AND FUND BALANCE

Accounts payable and accrued employee benefits	\$ 46,453
Grants and fellowships payable	1,151,133
Federal excise taxes payable	3,746
Deferred income (Note 2)	5,987,480
Total liabilities	<u>7,188,812</u>

Unrestricted fund balance

Appropriated	\$174,677	
Unappropriated	<u>625,952</u>	<u>800,629</u>
Total liabilities and fund balance		<u>\$7,989,441</u>

Council on Library Resources, Inc.

Statement of Revenues, Expenses and Changes in Fund Balance

For the Year Ended June 30, 1980

	Unrestricted	Restricted	Total
Revenues (Note 2)			
Grants and contracts	\$700,000	\$1,086,813	\$1,786,813
Investment income	185,736		185,736
Royalty income	1,526		1,526
Total revenues	<u>887,262</u>	<u>1,086,813</u>	<u>1,974,075</u>
Expenses (Notes 2 and 3)			
Program services	497,297	1,086,813	1,584,110
Administrative services	233,267		233,267
Total expenses	<u>730,564</u>	<u>1,086,813</u>	<u>1,817,377</u>
Excess of revenues over expenses	156,698		156,698
Fund balance, beginning of year	<u>643,931</u>		<u>643,931</u>
Fund balance, end of year	<u>\$800,629</u>	<u>\$</u>	<u>\$ 800,629</u>

Council on Library Resources, Inc.

Statement of Changes in Cash and Short-Term Investments

For the Year Ended June 30, 1980

Sources of cash and short-term investments

Excess of revenues over expenses from operations	\$ 156,698
Increase in grants, contracts and fellowships payable	433,732
Increase in federal excise taxes, accounts payable and accrued employee benefits	17,779
Decrease in grants receivable	<u>537,766</u>
	<u>1,145,975</u>

Uses of cash

Decrease in deferred income	716,812
Increase in accrued royalties	162
Increase in prepaid expenses and deposits	<u>3,575</u>
	<u>720,549</u>

Increase in cash and short-term investments for the year	425,426
Cash and short-term investments, beginning of year	<u>1,555,995</u>
Cash and short-term investments, end of year	<u>\$1,981,421</u>

Council on Library Resources, Inc.

Notes to Financial Statements

June 30, 1980

1. Organization

The Council on Library Resources, Inc. (Council) is a non-profit organization incorporated under the laws of the District of Columbia in 1956 for the purpose of promoting library research. The Council's operations are financed primarily through two five-year unrestricted general support grants from The Ford Foundation and The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation and through several restricted grants and contracts from private foundations and other sources. The Council conducts its work through directly administered projects as well as grants to and contracts with other organizations or individuals.

The Council is a private operating foundation and is exempt from Federal income tax under Internal Revenue Code section 501(c)(3). It is, however, subject to a 2% excise tax on investment and royalty income under the provisions of the Revenue Act of 1978.

2. Summary of Significant Accounting Policies

The Council's financial statements are prepared on the accrual basis. Grants are recorded as receivable at such time as the Council is notified that it has been awarded the funds. Unrestricted grant revenue is recognized in accordance with the budgeted annual payments specified by the grantors. Interest and royalty income are recognized as unrestricted grant revenue. Restricted grant revenue is recognized to the extent of the related expenses. Grant, contract, and fellowship expenses are recorded when the recipients are notified that they are to receive the funds. All unrecognized grant revenue is recorded as deferred income.

The costs of office furniture and equipment are consistently charged to expense when incurred. The Council does not consider such expenditures to be sufficiently material to warrant capitalization and depreciation.

3. Functional Allocation of Expenses

The Council's costs of providing program and administrative services for the year ended June 30, 1980 are summarized in the schedule that follows.

	Unrestricted	Restricted	Total
Expenses			
Program services			
Grants, fellowships and contracts	\$266,684	\$ 950,204	\$1,216,888
Council-administered projects	33,289	140,165	173,454
Less adjustments resulting from excess allocations of grants and fellowships	(23,545)	(3,556)	(27,101)
Compensation and employee benefits	199,477		199,477
Other expenses	21,392		21,392
	<u>497,297</u>	<u>1,086,813</u>	<u>1,584,110</u>
Administrative services			
Compensation and employee benefits	121,562		121,562
Rent	43,391		43,391
Travel and meetings	18,096		18,096
Other	50,218		50,218
	<u>233,267</u>		<u>233,267</u>
Total expenses	<u>\$730,564</u>	<u>\$1,086,813</u>	<u>\$1,817,377</u>

4. Retirement Plan

Employees are eligible for participation in the Council's retirement annuity program, which is administered through the TIAA/CREF insurance companies. Individual contracts issued under the plan provide for full and immediate vesting of both the Council's and employees' contributions. The Council's contribution amounted to \$42,000 for fiscal year 1980.

5. Commitments

The Council is committed to a lease for office space expiring in 1982 which provides for minimum annual rentals of approximately \$45,000.

Supplementary Statement of Revenues, Expenses and Changes in Fund Balances

For the Year Ended June 30, 1980

	Unrestricted				Restricted				
	Ford Foundation	Mellon Foundation	Other	Total	Bibliographic Service Development Program (Note 2)	International Programs (Note 3)	National Library of Medicine	Total	Total
Revenues									
Grants and contracts	\$500,000	\$200,000		\$700,000	\$972,415	\$100,000	\$14,398	\$1,086,813	\$1,786,813
Investment income			\$185,736	185,736					185,736
Royalty income			1,526	1,526					1,526
Total revenues	<u>500,000</u>	<u>200,000</u>	<u>187,262</u>	<u>887,262</u>	<u>972,415</u>	<u>100,000</u>	<u>14,398</u>	<u>1,086,813</u>	<u>1,974,075</u>
Expenses (Note 1)									
Program services									
Grants, fellowships and contracts	194,679	72,005		266,684	849,916	100,000	288	950,204	1,216,888
Council-administered projects	24,301	8,988		33,289	124,999		15,166	140,165	173,454
Less adjustments resulting from excess allocations of grants and fellowships	(17,188)	(6,357)		(23,545)	(2,500)		(1,056)	(3,556)	(27,101)
Compensation and employee benefits	145,618	53,859		199,477					199,477
Professional fees	6,775	2,505		9,280					9,280
Travel and meetings	8,065	2,983		11,048					11,048
Other expenses	777	287		1,064					1,064
	<u>363,027</u>	<u>134,270</u>		<u>497,297</u>	<u>972,415</u>	<u>100,000</u>	<u>14,398</u>	<u>1,086,813</u>	<u>1,584,110</u>
Administrative services									
Compensation and employee benefits	88,740	32,822		121,562					121,562
Travel and meetings	13,210	4,886		18,096					18,096
Professional fees	5,615	2,076		7,691					7,691
Rent	31,675	11,716		43,391					43,391
Equipment rental and furniture	2,879	1,065		3,944					3,944
Printing	7,492	2,771		10,263					10,263
Office and other expenses	17,939	6,635	3,746	28,320					28,320
	<u>167,550</u>	<u>61,971</u>	<u>3,746</u>	<u>233,267</u>					<u>233,267</u>
Total expenses	<u>530,577</u>	<u>196,241</u>	<u>3,746</u>	<u>730,564</u>	<u>972,415</u>	<u>100,000</u>	<u>14,398</u>	<u>1,086,813</u>	<u>1,817,377</u>
Excess of revenues over expenses	(30,577)	3,759	183,516	156,698					156,698
Fund balance, beginning of year	402,589	126,402	114,940	643,931					643,931
Fund balance, end of year	<u>\$372,012</u>	<u>\$130,161</u>	<u>\$298,456</u>	<u>\$800,629</u>	<u>\$</u>	<u>\$</u>	<u>\$</u>	<u>\$</u>	<u>\$ 800,629</u>

Council on Library Resources, Inc.

Notes to Supplementary Statement of Revenues, Expenses and Changes in Fund Balances

For the Year Ended June 30, 1980

1. Allocation of Expenses

Under the terms of the Ford and Mellon foundations' unrestricted general support grants, the Council must account for expenditures of these funds on an individual basis. The Council allocates these expenses between the Ford and Mellon grants based upon the ratio of the sums of the respective fund balances at the beginning of the year and current year's revenue. Unrestricted expenses related to investment and royalty income are excluded from the Ford and Mellon allocation process.

2. Bibliographic Service Development Program

The Council has been awarded restricted grants totalling \$4,600,000 for this program from the following sources: the Carnegie Corporation of New York, The Commonwealth Fund, The Ford Foundation, The William and Flora Hewlett Foundation, the Lilly Endowment, Inc., The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation, the National Endowment for the Humanities and the Alfred P. Sloan Foundation. The purpose of these grants is to fund a five-year research and development project to assist in establishing primary components of a national bibliographic system. The Council currently estimates the costs of this project to be \$6,100,000. Additional funding from various sources will be sought as the project progresses.

3. International Programs

During 1979 and 1980 the Council was awarded two restricted grants totalling \$200,000 from the Exxon Education Foundation in general support for the Council's international activities.

4. Future Program

In June 1980, the Council was awarded a \$650,000 restricted grant from The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation to partially fund a new program of professional education and training for research librarians. It is anticipated that work will begin early in fiscal year 1981. Additional funding is being sought to meet the full cost of the program.

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Program Guidelines

The Council on Library Resources, Inc. is a private operating foundation. Established in 1956 by the Ford Foundation, the Council continues to receive support from it as well as other foundations. Over the years the Council has sought to be of assistance to those who are concerned with the quality of library operations and the character of library service, primarily in collegiate and research libraries. Through research, development, demonstration, and dissemination of results, CLR seeks to reduce obstacles that hamper those who need and seek information.

How CLR Works

The Council awards grants to individuals and organizations for projects that fall within CLR program interests and hold promise of meeting stated goals. The Council's present concerns include:

- bibliographic services
- library resources and their preservation
- library operations and services
- professional education and training

Proposals are reviewed internally in accordance with established procedures. In addition, the Council frequently involves consultants in the evaluation of proposals on a confidential basis.

As an operating foundation, the Council also initiates and administers a limited number of specific programs. Occasionally, the Council enters into contractual arrangements.

CLR acts as a catalyst, often bringing together the expertise of many people and organizations for a mutual exploration of a major issue. It is a coordinating agency, organizing participation in certain cooperative undertakings. Finally, it provides consulta-

tion services when requested in areas where help is needed but funding is either not sought or not possible.

What Will Not Be Funded

No foundation can support all the legitimate needs of libraries. From the beginning the Council has established a policy of not providing support for certain categories of activity in order to concentrate on programs where funding is either limited or nonexistent. Thus CLR does not entertain proposals for building construction or improvement, purchase of collections or equipment, or normal staffing or operational costs. Because the Council attempts to support programs that will result in benefits to many libraries, grants are not provided for programs that will be useful only to the institutions in which they take place.

Application Procedures

Initial inquiries regarding possible project support should be in the form of a letter, which should include the following information:

1. Name and address of requester and of proposed principal investigator, if they differ.
2. Type of institution.
3. Tax status.
4. A clear statement of the aims of the project, its significance, the general approach and specific research methods to be used.
5. Amount of request and proposed budget.
6. Period to be covered by project.

If a proposal is judged to be of possible interest, advice will be offered as to proposal preparation and additional information may be requested. All inquiries should be addressed to Warren J. Haas, President, Council on Library Resources, 1 Dupont Circle, Suite 620, Washington, D.C. 20036.

